

**HISTOPATHOLOGICAL STUDY OF
ADIPOCYTES AFTER MICROLIPOINJECTION**

Thesis

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Introduction

INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

Soft tissue augmentation of facial rhytids, scars, and deformities is frequently performed. Nowadays the ease, cost, and minimal discomfort associated with injectable soft tissue fillers make it an ideal procedure. Numerous soft tissue fillers are available for soft tissue augmentation.

An ideal injectable soft tissue filler is one that is inexpensive, easy to use, biocompatible, nonpyrogenic, nontoxic, noncarcinogenic, nonallergenic, nonimmunogenic, and nonmigratory, and one with long-lasting effects. The quest for finding an ideal injectable soft tissue filler has resulted in the discovery of many biologic and alloplastic implants over the years; however, the ideal implant has not been found.^(1,2)

The alloplastic injectable soft tissue fillers are composed of silicone, Bioplastique (Bioplasty, St. Paul, MN), and polymethylmethacrylate. Alloplastic implants create permanent soft tissue augmentation, which is the major advantage over biologic implants. Unfortunately, there are no alloplastic implants currently approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in the United States.

Current biologic implants include autologous, allogenic, and xenogenic materials, such as bovine collagen, autologous collagen, allogenic collagen, autologous fibroblasts, autologous fat, gelatin matrix, hyaluronic acid gels, preserved particulate fascia lata, and micronized Alloderm (LifeCell Corp, Branchburg, NJ). Although these implants are biocompatible, reabsorption and lack of permanency are their main disadvantages. Currently, only biologic implants are available in the United States for soft tissue augmentation.

Alloplastic Implants

Silicone

Silicone is a polymer of dimethylpolysiloxane that is available in various forms, ranging from liquid to solid. Liquid silicone is a clear, colorless, inert fluid derived from silica. Injectable silicone is not FDA approved in the United States, but has been used as an injectable implant in Asia, Europe, and Latin America.^(3,4)

Silicone is injected through a 30-gauge needle in microdroplets of 0.01 mL into the subdermis. The serial injections should be separated by 1 to 2 mm of tissue. Each microdroplet induces its own fibroblastic response, resulting in augmentation. Injectable silicone produces soft tissue augmentation by forming a fibrous capsule around each particle of silicone. This process takes several weeks. One should inject microamounts and undercorrect. Repeated treatments 6 weeks apart may be necessary for adequate augmentation.^(4,5)

Silicone is permanent; however, the disadvantages are numerous, including inflammation, induration, discoloration, ulceration, migration, and formation of silicone granulomas. Silicone also is difficult to remove once it is injected into the soft tissue. There are those who believe that the complications seen with silicone are caused by improper technique in injecting silicone, injecting too much silicone, or the quality of the silicone.^(3,4,5)

Bioplastique

Bioplastique, developed in 1987, currently is not available as an injectable filler. Bioplastique consists of a biphasic polymer with a solid phase of vulcanized

silicone rubber microparticles suspended in a liquid phase of biocompatible plasdone hydrogel. The gel is excreted unchanged from the kidneys in a few days. The gel is replaced by fibrin in 3 days and eventually collagen. The microparticles are 100 to 400 μm in diameter, which are too large to be ingested by macrophages or to allow migration. The microparticles are textured to allow fibrous tissue ingrowth. Augmentation occurs over several weeks by formation of a fibrous capsule around the microparticles. Undercorrection is recommended.^(6,7,8)

Bioplastique is injected into the subcutaneous tissue (not the dermis) with a special 20-gauge cannula and a high-pressure leverage gun. Before injection of Bioplastique, the area to be augmented is infiltrated with lidocaine and epinephrine for anesthesia and vasoconstriction. The cannula should be moved rapidly while the Bioplastique is injected slowly. Overcorrection should be avoided. Additional injections can be performed 6 weeks later, if necessary.⁽⁹⁾

Polymethylmethacrylate

Artecoll (Rofil Medical International, The Netherlands) is permanent injectable soft tissue filler that is currently not FDA approved but is available in Europe and Canada. It is a suspension of polymethylmethacrylate microspheres in 3.5% bovine collagen solution. The microspheres are 30 to 40 μm in size with a smooth surface. The smooth surface is reported to cause less foreign body reaction than a rough surface. The size of the microspheres allows injection through a 27-gauge needle, but prevents migration and phagocytosis. The microspheres are encapsulated by a fine fibrous capsule within 2 to 4 months, whereas the collagen solution is degraded by the body within 1 to 3 months.⁽¹⁰⁾

Artecoll is indicated in treating facial rhytids or scars and lip augmentation. Areas of thin skin, such as crow's feet, should be avoided because the implant may be visible or palpable. It should not be used to correct defects of the subcutaneous fat. Artecoll is contraindicated in patients who are allergic to collagen; who have thin, flaccid skin or an atrophic skin disease; and who form keloids.⁽¹⁰⁾

Artecoll is injected into the subdermis with a 27-gauge needle under constant pressure. The needle should be drawn back and forth, creating tunnels. It should never be infiltrated into the dermis. Slight overcorrection is recommended. The area should be massaged once the injection is completed. Repeated injections should be performed 1 to 3 months after the initial injection, if necessary.⁽¹⁰⁾

Artecoll creates long-lasting soft tissue augmentation; however, error in placement can result in permanent disfigurement. Intradermal placement of Artecoll can result in swelling, pain, persistent erythema, and visible or palpable granules. Pruritis or hypertrophic scarring can occur at the implantation site. Allergic reactions also can occur because the implant is suspended in bovine collagen. Skin testing is mandatory.⁽¹⁰⁾

Biologic Implants

Bovine Collagen

Injectable collagen is a reconstituted, purified, enzyme-digested, bovine dermal collagen suspended in a phosphate-buffered saline with 0.3% lidocaine. Zyderm I (McGhan Medical, Santa Barbara, CA) was approved by the FDA in 1981 and contains a collagen concentration of 35 mg/mL (95% of type I collagen and 5% of type III collagen). Rapid reabsorption of Zyderm I led to the development of

Zyderm II (McGhan Medical, Santa Barbara, CA) and Zyplast (McGhan Medical, Santa Barbara, CA), which were FDA-approved in 1983 and 1985, respectively. Zyderm II is similar to Zyderm I, but contains a higher concentration of collagen (65 mg/mL). Zyplast differs from Zyderm I and II in that it contains glutaraldehyde cross-linked collagen, which is less susceptible to collagenase degradation and less immunogenic. Zyplast has a collagen concentration of 35 mg/mL.^(3,11)

Bovine collagen is indicated for the correction of facial rhytids and scars (e.g., post-acne, post-traumatic, post-viral, and postoperative) and lip augmentation. It is contraindicated, however, in patients with autoimmune disease, anaphylactoid reactions, lidocaine hypersensitivity, and previous bovine collagen hypersensitivity. Patients on immunosuppressive therapy and patients with a history of chronic inflammatory disease, however, should not receive augmentation with bovine collagen. Injections of bovine collagen should be avoided in sites of active inflammation and infection.^(11,12)

Bovine collagen may induce an allergic reaction; skin testing is mandatory. Skin tests are manufactured in 0.1-mL aliquots of Zyderm I. The test implant is injected intradermally on the flexor surface of the forearm. Erythema, induration, tenderness, or swelling with or without pruritis at the injection site indicates a positive skin test. These symptoms generally occur within the first 48 to 72 hours; however, the site is monitored for a total of 4 weeks. Three percent of the general population is allergic to bovine collagen, and develops an initial positive skin test. One percent to 2% of nonallergic patients develop a hypersensitivity reaction after implantation of collagen, although the skin test was negative; a second skin test on the contralateral arm is recommended 2 to 4 weeks later.^(5,13)

Zyderm and Zyplast are injected intradermally. Zyderm is infiltrated into the superficial papillary dermis, whereas Zyplast is placed into the midreticular or deep reticular dermis at the dermal subcutaneous interface. Zyplast should not be injected into the superficial papillary dermis or in areas of thin skin because it forms beads on placement.⁽¹¹⁾

Overcorrection of bovine collagen is mandatory because the water that is admixed with the bovine collagen is reabsorbed within 24 hours after injection. Zyderm I should be corrected by 150% to 200%, whereas Zyderm II should be corrected by less. There are those who recommend not overcorrecting Zyplast, but the authors have seen better results with slight overcorrection.⁽¹¹⁾

Zyderm I and Zyderm II are used to correct superficial rhytids, whereas Zyplast is used to efface deeper rhytids. Zyplast should not be used in areas of thin skin, such as for crow's feet, because of the possibility of visible beading. Tissue necrosis with resultant scarring also can occur because of compression of the dermal vasculature or intravascular injection especially if Zyplast is used in the glabella. Although rare, blindness has been reported with Zyplast injection of the glabella as a result of retrograde occlusion of the retinal artery; Zyplast is contraindicated in the glabella.^(11,13)

Another indication for bovine collagen is the correction of post-acne, post-traumatic, post-viral, and postoperative scars. Not all depressed scars respond to collagen injection. Scars that are bound deeply down, such as ice-pick acne scars, have a dense stroma that does not allow infiltration of collagen. To determine which scars can be corrected with collagen injection, a stretch test can be performed. The skin lateral to the scar is stretched, if the scar flattens out with this maneuver, it can

be corrected with collagen augmentation. The authors prefer treating scars with Zyplast.⁽¹¹⁾

The advantages of bovine collagen are that it is easy to use, readily available, and can be performed with a minimal amount of pain. The main disadvantage of injectable collagen is its lack of permanent soft tissue augmentation. Repeat injections are required every 3 to 4-months. Other disadvantages of injectable collagen include allergic reactions, intermittent swelling, and cystic reactions at the injection site.⁽¹¹⁾

Autologous Collagen

Autologen (Collagenesis, Beverly, MA) is an injectable autologous human tissue matrix, primarily composed of intact collagen fibrils. It is processed from the patient's own skin that is harvested during skin excision surgery, such as rhytidectomy. Once excised, the skin is shipped to Collagenesis and processed. Two square inches of skin are required to fill a syringe (1 mL) of Autologen, which can be refrigerated for 6 months. Autologen should be removed from refrigeration 1 hour before use, and should be allowed to warm to room temperature.^(1,14)

The human tissue collagen matrix is diluted to a 5% suspension so that intact collagen fibers can be delivered with ease through a 30-gauge needle into the dermis-like bovine collagen. The soft tissue defect should be overcorrected by at least 20% to 30%. Because the Autologen syringes do not contain lidocaine, Autologen injections are more painful than Zyplast or Zyderm. Nerve blocks or local or topical anesthesia may be needed for patient comfort and tolerance. Unlike bovine collagen, at least three injections are required over several weeks to augment a soft tissue defect adequately. Most injectate is resorbed because of the low 5% concentration of collagen.⁽¹⁾

Autologen seems to last for 3 to 6 months. Disadvantages of Autologen include pain with injection, unknown duration of implant persistence, and the time required for harvesting and sending donor tissue for processing. The advantages of Autologen are that there is no risk for disease transmission or allergic reaction because the material is autologous. Skin testing is not required for Autologen.^(14,15)

Allogeneic Collagen

Dermalogen (Collagenesis, Beverly, MA) is a suspension of injectable human tissue collagen matrix prepared from human donor tissue. Dermalogen is like Autologen, except that it is processed from cadaver tissue that has undergone extensive screening for viral and bacterial contamination.^(1,16)

Dermalogen can be refrigerated up to 6 months, and should be removed from refrigeration 1 hour before injection. Dermalogen is injected into the dermis with a 30-gauge needle. Like Autologen, Dermalogen injections are painful and serial injections (usually three) over several weeks are required for adequate soft tissue augmentation. Overcorrection of at least 20% to 30% is recommended with each injection. In the authors' experience, the duration of augmentation with Dermalogen is similar to bovine collagen (3 months).^(1,16)

The advantage of Dermalogen is that there have been no reported cases of allergic reaction. Skin testing is not required by the FDA. Dermalogen can be used in patients allergic to bovine collagen. The disadvantages of Dermalogen are its lack of permanency and cost. Dermalogen is two to three times more expensive than

collagen for the same results because at least three syringes of Dermalogen are required for adequate augmentation.⁽¹⁾

Autologous Fibroblasts

Human fibroblasts now can be grown in tissue culture and harvested for injection into soft tissue deficits. Isolagen (Isolagen Technologies, Paramus, NJ) is injectable autologous fibroblasts cultured for 4 to 6 weeks from a 3-mm punch biopsy taken from postauricular skin.⁽¹⁷⁾

A test dose is administered first, followed by a 1-mL injection into the superficial or mid-dermis in 2 weeks. Three to four injections should be performed over a 3- to 6-month period.

Disadvantages of Isolagen are that it is expensive and must be injected into a soft tissue defect the day after being processed and shipped overnight because the cultured fibroblasts are alive and cannot be stored. The advantage of Isolagen is that there have been no reported allergic reactions. Isolagen temporarily has been withdrawn from the market, pending FDA approval.⁽¹⁷⁾

Gelatin Matrix Implant (Fibrel)

The mechanism of action of Fibrel is based on normal wound healing. Tissue injury leads to release of clotting factors with the formation of fibrinogen to fibrin. Fibroblastic proliferation occurs with formation of new collagen. Currently, it is no longer available.^(15,18,19)

Hyaluronic Acid Derivatives

Hyaluronic acid gels recently have been developed for intradermal injection to augment soft tissue. They currently are not FDA-approved, but are available outside the United States. Hyaluronic acid, which is identical in all species, is a glycosaminoglycan biopolymer found naturally in the dermis. It has a high affinity to bind water, leading to increased hydration and skin turgor. Hyaluronic acid concentration decreases with age, which causes dermal dehydration and rhytid formation.^(16,20)

Hyaluronic acid, by itself, when injected into the dermis, is rapidly degraded and cleared by the liver. Hyaluronic acid gels were developed by cross-linking hyaluronic acid chains to increase their longevity. Hyaluronic acid gels are more viscous and less water soluble; however, they are eventually broken down and cleared, such as hyaluronic acid.^(16,20)

Currently, there are two commercially available hyaluronic acid derivatives. Hyalform, also known as Hylan B (Biomatrix, Ridgefield, NJ), is derived from rooster comb and is cross-linked. Restylane (Q-Med, Upsala, Sweden) is a partially cross-linked hyaluronic acid processed from bacterial (*Streptococcus*) fermentation. Hyaluronic acid gels are injected into the dermis with 30-gauge needles. A touch-up injection may be necessary 2 to 4 weeks later.⁽¹⁶⁾

An advantage of hyaluronic acid gels is that there is little risk for hypersensitivity; a skin test is not required. Another advantage of Restylane is that it is not derived from an animal source. Although the soft tissue augmentation obtained from hyaluronic acid gels is temporary, it does seem to last longer than bovine collagen, with a reported duration of at least 3 to 6 months. Immediate adverse effects with injection of hyaluronic acid gels, including intermittent swelling

at site of injection, erythema, edema, and pain (there is no anesthetic mixed with the material), have been reported. There are no major reported systemic side effects.^(15,16,20)

Preserved Particulate Fascia Lata

Preserved irradiated human cadaver fascia lata, inserted intradermally, stimulates native collagen formation in post-traumatic and acne scars. This process is known as recollagenation. Fascian (Fascia Biosystems, Beverly Hills, CA), which recently has become available, is preserved particulate fascia lata that can be injected for soft tissue augmentation. Fascian is derived from human screened cadaver donors. There are three available particle sizes (<2 mm, <0.5 mm, <0.25 mm). Fascian must be rehydrated with 3 mL of 0.3% lidocaine or saline before injection. The implant is injected into the subdermis with a 16- or 18-gauge needle for the less than 2.0-mm particles, with a 20-gauge needle for the less than 0.5-mm particles, and with a 22-gauge needle for the less than 0.25 particles.⁽²¹⁻²²⁾ Long-term studies must evaluate this injectable soft tissue filler further.

Micronized Alloderm

Alloderm is an acellular, freeze-dried, dermal graft harvested from screened cadavers and processed to remove all cellular and antigenic components, leaving a matrix of dermal elements (i.e., collagen, elastin, glycosaminoglycans). No reported cases of disease transmission exist. Cymetra (LifeCell, Branchburg, NJ) is micronized Alloderm created as an injectable soft tissue filler, newly available in the United States.^(16,23)

Cymetra must be reconstituted with 1 mL of lidocaine before injection and used within 2 hours. The manufacturer recommends infiltration of Cymetra into the subdermis with a 26-gauge needle. Long-term benefits of injectable Alloderm are not known currently.⁽²³⁾

Autologous fat transplantation

History

In 1893, Neuber taught that fat tissue could survive as a transplant into scarred areas, but only in tiny parcels. The idea of fat surviving as small parcels of tissue is an important component of the recipe for successful autotransplantation of fat. In 1910, Erich Lexer used autologous fat to repair caved-in areas after fracture along the zygomatic arch. He reported that a 12-by 3-cm block of tissue harvested from the subcutaneous abdominal wall yielded an excellent result. By 1922, he documented survival of longer than 3 years for fatty transplants. Lexer warned, "It is necessary that the fat tissue is not damaged at the moment of its implantation ... (and)... its viability is not reduced by a hemorrhage occurring at the site of implantation. His studies showed that fatty tissue is fragile and even slight trauma to the tissues during harvest, transport or implantation will jeopardize survival. The importance of this observation cannot be underestimated."^(24,25,26)

In the 1950s, Peer demonstrated that free fatty tissue transplants had 50% survival rates. He postulated that neovascularization occurs in small fat parcels after about 4 days, and that the cells survived on diffusion for the first few days. The literature has continued to demonstrate that transplanted fatty tissue can create a lasting correction.⁽²⁷⁻³⁰⁾ Also many techniques are documented that transfer fat in a

traumatic fashion, make the fat partially or wholly disappear.⁽³¹⁻³³⁾ Unfortunately, plastic surgeons have dwelled on the reports of failure rather than pinpointing the elements of successful fat grafting. When plastic surgeons examine a study such as Peer's, the emphasis is placed on the 50% that died, not on the 50% that lived.

In spite of the warnings by Lexer and Neuber in the early part of the century, even the most skilful contemporary plastic surgeons traumatize the fatty tissue by mechanical trauma: straining, whisking, filtering, washing high negative pressure harvesting and high positive pressure injecting. With these traumatic manipulations and widely varying techniques, it is no surprise that the divergent reports of tissue survival have left autologous tissue transplantation shrouded in controversy.^(24,27,30,34,35)

Development of Lipostructure

Around 1986. All of the techniques appeared traumatic to the transplanted tissue. They harvested big globules of fat and processed it so that it would fit through a smaller needle. High negative pressures were used for harvesting, and high positive pressures were used for injecting fat. The refining and transferring maneuvers seemed damaging to the tissue. In short, the maneuvers of all of the techniques existing in 1986 seemed to violate the vulnerable. Fragile nature of a fatty tissue not intended to survive outside the human body.⁽³⁶⁾

Coleman invented a new technique that transplant fat as tissue, not as individual cell. Rather than attempting to reduce the size of the fat after it was harvested, this technique harvested the fat as an intact tissue parcel already of a size that could easily slide through a smaller needle. Exposure of the fragile fatty tissue to atmospheric pressure changes and to air was minimized. Most of the oil, blood, and lidocaine were removed gently from the harvested tissue by sedimentation or centrifugation. The parcels of fatty tissue were placed in such a fashion that each parcel would be close to a nutritional and respiratory source and could anchor itself to the surrounding tissues. The longevity of fat transplanted by the method of Lipostructure has been documented in progressive reports⁽³⁷⁻³⁹⁾

Coleman has found that transplanted fatty tissue harvested with care, transplanted atraumatically, and appropriately infiltrated has every indication of permanence.⁽³⁶⁾

Indications

Injection of fat obtained by liposuction and used as an autologous graft has become a more frequent procedure in plastic surgery for improvements in the face and body contour to eliminate deep defects in the skin surface for cosmetic and reconstructive purposes^(40,41).

The most frequent regions treated were cheeks, nasolabial folds, perioral wrinkles, labial contour, chin, periorbital wrinkles (crowsfeet), and glabella. Fat injection also was used for the correction of contour irregularities from excess fat removal as well as for wrinkled skin on the knees, thin ankles, and gluteal depressions. Also fat autotransplantation is used for correction of localized steroid induced atrophy⁽⁴⁰⁻⁴⁴⁾.

There are two primary reasons for facial augmentation: replacement of atrophied or missing facial structures and enhancement of facial elements. A common goal of both of these indications is to create more harmonious and aesthetically appealing proportion of the face.

Aging and acne both erode the structures under the skin to leave behind an emptier sac of skin that is suitable for filling and restructuring with Lipostructure. Other acquired and congenital processes also leave the face with bony and soft-tissue deficiencies that are amenable to correction with this technique. Common examples include burns, soft-tissue trauma, facial fractures, iatrogenic nasal deformities, secondary cleft lip deformities, mid-face hypoplasia, micrognathia, hemi-facial atrophy, and other syndromes involving atrophy such as Rhombert's hemifacial atrophy.⁽³⁶⁾

Even normal facial structures can be aided by Lipostructure. Adding constructive elements can correct a broad range of perceived facial deficiencies. A stronger jawline creates a healthier, more powerful face. Eliminating the tear gutter deformity and hollowness of lower eyelids eliminate the tired, sad appearance.⁽³⁶⁾

Calmer glabellar frown lines make a person look less anxious or angry. Sensual lips give a healthier appearance.⁽³⁶⁾

Lipostructure is also particularly suited for reconstructing the proportion of the face. By enlarging the jawline or lip, the chin becomes relatively smaller. Enhancement of specific facial elements can improve overall facial harmony and proportion.

The technique of lipostructure:

Method of harvesting a small intact parcel of fatty tissue and refining it to remove the nonviable components while avoiding mechanical trauma or exposure. Gentle positive pressure transports fatty parcels through small cannulae to implant the graft in a manner that provides nutrition and anchors the fat to the host tissues.⁽³⁶⁾

Harvesting

Strict sterile technique must be always observed. Donor sites are chosen to improve body contour and avoid deformities. Donor areas are: Abdomen, knee, trochanter, buttock, hip, pubis and inner part of the thigh⁽⁴⁵⁾. Epidural anesthesia is preferred for harvesting. Ringers lactate with 1:40000 of epinephrine are infiltrated bluntly through a stab incision prior to harvesting. If only a limited amount of tissue is to be harvested, the epidural can be substituted with local anesthesia of 0.5% lidocaine with 1:200,000 epinephrine.⁽³⁶⁾

The harvesting device is a 10-mL disposable Luer-lock syringe attached to a two-holed blunt cannula. The entry portal of the cannula is just large enough to allow passage of fatty tissue parcels of a size that then will pass through the lumen of the tip of the Luerlock syringe. To limit the vacuum to minimal negative pressure, suction is hand applied by slowly withdrawing the plunger of the 10-ml syringe in a gradual manner. The harvesting relies on a curretting action aided by suctioning.^(46,49)

Transfer and Purification

The harvesting cannula is disconnected from the Luer-lock and is replaced by a cap. The plunger of the syringe then is removed. The capped 10-mL syringe is placed into a sterilized sleeve in a sterilized central rotor of text continued on a centrifuge and spun at about 3000 rpm for 2 or 3 minutes.

The aspirated subcutaneous material separates into three basic layers: the top, least dense layer is composed primarily of oil from ruptured parcels of fat; the bottom, most dense layer is composed almost entirely of blood and lidocaine or Ringer's lactate; and the middle layer consists primarily of usable subcutaneous tissue.

The top oil layer is decanted and the dense lowest layer is drained. Nasal packing or a neuro-pad then is placed into the top of the remaining tissue layer to wick off more of the remaining oil. The refined parcels of fats are then transferred to a 1-mL or 3-mL Luer- Lock syringe. With the exception of the wick for removing oil, no foreign substances of any type are ever placed in the harvested fatty tissue.⁽³⁶⁾

Placement

Receptor areas:

Forehead, temple, glabella, crow's feet, malar area, zygomatic area, pseudonasolabial folds, pseudojowls, hollow cheeks, nasolabial folds, preparotid, masseterine, chin, upper and lower lip (Vermillion lines), commissure of mouth and commissure fold, depressed scars,	postliposuction and post-traumatic surgical irregularities, hands, forearm, arm, armpit, trochanter, buttock, thigh, knee, ankle, acne scars, atrophies and hemifacial atrophies ⁽⁴⁵⁾ .
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The recipient area is anesthetized by a combination of regional nerve blocks and local infiltration of 0.5% lidocaine with 1:100,000 of epinephrine. The lipoinfiltrator is an 18-gauge cannula with an ejection aperture close to the closed distal end. The ejection portal is just large enough to allow passage of the parcels of fatty tissue. The intact parcels are forced out of the ejection aperture by depressing the plunger on the infiltrating syringe. The size, shape, and internal finish of the cannula is designed to reduce clogging and trauma to the parcels of fatty tissue. The distal end is blunt to reduce the chance of hematomas, nerve damage, and perforation of nontargeted tissues. The length, shape, curvature, and size of the cannula can be varied to facilitate technical considerations. The cannula is connected to a 1-mL or a 3-mL syringe filled with refined fatty tissue.

Access to areas is obtained by appropriately placed 1-or 2-mm incisions made with a # 11 blade. The lipoinfiltrator is inserted through these incisions to create tunnels by the advancement of the cannula through the recipient tissue. As the cannula through is withdrawn, the plunger of the syringe is depressed in a controlled manner so that a minuscule amount of the refined tissue (usually less than 1/8 of a ml) is placed evenly over the length of the tunnel. Only minimal positive pressure is ever placed on the plunger of the infiltration syringe. If any significant resistance is encountered the cannula is disconnected immediately from the syringe and any offending plug is removed.

Postoperative care

Compression dressings are applied around the infiltrated areas if there is any suspicion of infection in the postoperative period. Stenting of areas of particular motion such as the glabella often is preformed. Usually simple paper tape is used to stabilize these areas. For 36 to 48 hours postoperatively, cold compresses or ice packs are applied continuously on all infiltrated sites.⁽³⁶⁾

Fat survival

Past experiments have shown that small amounts of fat may be transplanted with an expected survival rate between 10 and 50 percent. For the first week or so, fat cells live by diffusion and then neovascularization enables them to continue viability.⁽³²⁾

The rationale is transplanting a limited amount of fat and placing it in contact with well-vascularized tissue.

The transplanted fat is revascularized in the centripetal manner. Its capacity to survive through the plasmatic imbibition from the edges is 0.5 to 1.5 mm. Thus, the single threads of the transplanted adipose tissue should not exceed 3mm in diameter. The larger single collections of fat are subject to liquification, central necrosis, and cyst formation. This, in addition to technical imperfections, was the reason for reports of remarkable resorption rates.⁽⁵⁰⁻⁵⁶⁾

Equal, multilayered distribution of narrow strings of fat promoted the revascularization process of fat without the stage of cystosteatonecrosis. The chance of healing was good because of the favorable volume/surface ratio. Fat absorption slows down after approximately 2 years, and (usually) after that, 40 percent to 50 percent of the original volume of fat is retained. This fat is revascularized and is susceptible to the volume changes after general weight gain by the patient. This confirms the earlier observations of Peer that free autogenous fat grafts may actually increase in size if the patient takes on an increase in adiposity that affects the particular fat system from which the graft was taken.^(51,55)

Did the surviving adipocyte undergo transformation by dedifferentiation to the preadipocyte stage and differentiation again into the mature adipocytes, or did they survive by revascularization of the vascular net in the connective tissue stroma of the fat? It is possible, however, that fat cells present a few years after transplantation are surviving or descendent fat cells from the original graft, as Peer and Smahel have noted.^(50,55)

At present, two fat survival theories exist that are based on microscopic examinations of the behavior of the fat autografts in the animal models. The host replacement theory postulates that the histiocytes would scavenge lipid material and eventually replace all adipose tissue. The more popular theory in recent years is the cell survival theory, which states that some of the graft adipose tissue survives after the host reaction subsides.⁽⁵⁰⁾

The technique of free autologous fat transplantation influences the take of the graft or rejection:

1- Choice of donor site.

The choice of the donor site can be a problem because many of the patients seeking augmentation of the facial contour are very thin. In general, the sites with soft and easily removable fat should be used: lower abdomen, upper inner thigh, or

trochanteric area. The fat in the femoral region is more suitable for transplantation than facial fat. Fat tissue in the lower half of the body has less connective tissue septa and thus is only sparsely vascularized. This decreases the amount of blood in suctioned fat. Extravasated blood is known to be a good media for bacterial growth.⁽⁵⁰⁾

2- Method of fat removal.

Fat manipulation should be delicate to avoid the destruction of the fat globules⁽⁴⁰⁾.

3- Method of preparation and transplantation.

Never submerge the fat graft in a saline solution. This action will change the natural morphology of the fat tissue and cause a loss of fibrin, which aids in adhesion of the injected material to the surrounding tissue⁽⁴⁰⁾.

Only injections of good tissue quality should be done. Broken-down fat cells, oil, or blood should be separated from the good tissue and should not be used⁽⁴⁰⁾.

4- Selection of the recipient site.

The most frequent regions treated with fat injection for cosmetic purpose were cheeks, nasolabial folds, perioral wrinkles, labial contour, chin, periorbital wrinkles(crowsfeet), and glabella⁽⁴⁰⁾.

5- Preparation of the recipient area.

The defined recipient area is prepared by local anesthesia after adequate sterilization and disinfection.

Contraindications and Complications:

Contraindications for this procedure are:

- 1-Poor quality skin.
- 2-Patients with psychological alterations and with no real indication for lipoinjection.
- 3- Old patients with considerable skin ptosis and need combined surgery.

Mistakes in performance of this method can be prevented by:

- 1- Thorough screening of patients.
- 2- Knowledge of the fat extraction technique.
- 3- Correct injection of material.

Fat must not be washed or mixed to prevent it from losing the fibrin, which helps the fat remains where injected. Fat must not be left in contact with the environment due to the risk of contamination. Injection must not be made in bolus form because this can provoke formation of cysts or pseudocysts. Postoperative treatment includes antibiotics and analgesics as well as strict control of the patient.

Local anesthesia is recommended with caution because of the changes in anatomic structure of the tissue caused by increasing tissue volume with anesthetic fluid and because of vasoconstriction when the anesthetic is combined with epinephrine in the receptor and donor areas⁽⁴⁰⁾.

Resorption in some areas may be caused by less vascularization resulting from previous liposuction procedures^(40,57).

Patients should always be told in the preoperative period why overcorrection is necessary, the average time of recovery, the possible unpredictable problems, and that a second and even a third fat injection procedure may be necessary.⁽⁴⁰⁾

The main question that still remains is, does the fat survive as a graft, and in what amount.

The histologic studies are conclusive that some fat really survive as a graft, but the rest is probably an inflammatory reaction. This reaction develops a certain volume of cells and connective tissue, which produces the desired volume in deep areas over a nonpredictable period. The long-term efficacy is still unknown⁽⁴⁰⁾.

The early results obtained, the increasing number of patients asking for the fat injection, and their high level of satisfaction makes us recommend this method as effective.⁽⁴⁰⁾

Ellenbogen states that "with all the fat tissue being discarded in present-day surgical procedures and all the aesthetic defects secondary to subcutaneous tissue loss, free fat should be considered as a replacement. While it is difficult not to sympathize with sentiment when faces with numerous contour defects and limited options for tissue replacement, it is also difficult to feel overly optimistic in the present situation. Autologous fat transplantation is a technique with too much potential to be discarded out of hand at this point. However it is also too early, and the preliminary results are too tenuous, to have any confidence about the future of autologous fat transplantation."⁽⁵⁸⁾

Aim of the Work

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The aim of this work is to study the histopathological changes of fat cells in cases of microlipoinjection of depressed areas after a period of six months.

Patient & Methods

PATIENT & METHODS

PATIENTS AND METHODS

A group of fifteen patients, having depressed areas and furrows indicated for correction by soft tissue augmentation, were selected for this study from the dermatology outpatient clinic of Alexandria main university hospital and dermatology outpatient clinic from Alexandria clinic of health insurance.

This group of patients was subjected to microlipoinjection by the conventional technique using large Luer-lock syringes and fine cannula to obtain fat, and reinjecting it into layers in the recipient area till full correction.

The lower abdomen was used as the donor site of fat for all cases. Both liposuction and lipoinjection were done under local anesthesia.

Follow up of patients was done by biopsy which was taken from the site of lipoinjection after a period of six months.

Histopathological study of fat cells obtained from site of lipoinjection was done using formalin fixed paraffin embedded tissue. Sections stained using hematoxyllin and eosin were examined by light microscopy.

All patients were subjected to:

1- History taking:

This included:

- General medical history.
- History of dermatological diseases whether acute e.g. herpes, chronic e.g. psoriasis.
- The cause of the soft tissue defect.
- History of bleeding diathesis or current use of agents that affect coagulation.
- History of autoimmune disease⁽⁵⁹⁾

2- Physical examination included:

- General physical examination for any disease process hinted at in the history taking, such as diabetes mellitus or dislipidemias⁽⁵⁹⁾
- Local dermatological examination for presence of any single or multiple skin lesions and their description, distribution and arrangement.
- Measurement of the weight, height, and calculation of the body mass index (BMI) according to the formula $BMI = \text{weight in kgms} / \text{height in m}^2$.
According to the BMI, people are divided into 5 groups; those below 22.5 are considered thin, from between 22.5 to below 25 are normal, from 25 to below 30 are of grade 1 obesity, between 30 and below 40 are of grade 2 obesity, and those above 40 are grade 3 obesity.^(60,61)
- Evaluation of the recipient area for:
 - a) Skin redundancy; patients with redundant skin are excluded.
 - b) The presence of ongoing disease process such as lupus erythromatosis or morphea as they affect the graft survival.
 - c) The presence of scars, distortions, dermal defects or depressions that should be known to be uncorrectable by fat graft from the start.⁽⁵⁰⁾
 - d) Any underlying tissue losses other than fat such as bone, cartilage and supporting structures.⁽⁵⁹⁾
- Inspection of the skin of both donor and recipient sites for the presence of:

- a) Infection: it should be cleared before grafting.
 - b) Dermatologic disease process such as acne vulgaris.
 - Inspection of the body contour and fat aggregates for selection of the proper donor site. This includes inspection of the hips, buttocks, abdomen, trochanteric areas, thighs and the medical aspects of the knees.⁽⁵⁹⁾
- 3- Diagnostic laboratory tests should be employed as indicated by the history and physical examinations for any underlying disease process.
- 4- Thorough explanation was done to the patients before the procedure about the technique, its limitations including the expected degree of improvement, the potential for long term survival of the implanted material and the possible complications.

Instruments and materials

The instruments set used in this study consist of the following:

1-Liposuction cannula:

Blunt distally closed ended cannula with three diagonal holes. 20cms in length, 3 mm in diameter with handle connector.(fig 1 a,b)

2-Lipoinjection cannula:

Blunt distally closed ended cannula, with one lateral hole. 15 cms in length, 2 mm in diameter with luer-lock connection. (fig 2 a,b)

3-Adaptor:

Adaptor with Luer-lock connection for use with liposuction cannula with handle connector on tommy syringes.(fig 3)

4-Snapper:

Aluminum stop (lock) for syringes, lock to maintain vaccum in syringes by stopping the pulled out plunger in place.(fig 4)

5-Multiple disposable plastic Luer-lock syringes, 60 ml for liposuction, 10 ml for lipoinjection, sterile, fitting with cannulas with Luer-lock connection and with adaptor.(fig 5)

Figure 1a: Suction cannula (3 mm) in diameter.

Figure 1b: Tripple hole blunt head.

Figure 2a: Injection cannula (2 mm) in diameter.

Figure 2b: Single hole blunt head.

Figure 3: Adaptor

Figure 4: Snapper

Figure 5: 60cc Luer-lock syringe
connected to suction cannula
connected to adaptor.

Procedure

Harvesting

Strict sterile technique always must be observed. Donor sites are chosen to improve body contour and avoid deformities. Sterilization and toweling of both donor and recipient areas. Donor area is then marked with a blue marker. Local anesthesia of 0.5% lidocaine, Ringer's lactate with 1:200,000 epinephrine previously prepared in a small container containing 50 ml Ringer's lactate + 1 ampoule of epinephrine 0.25mg is infiltrated bluntly prior to harvesting through a 30ml syringe filled with 10ml 0.5% lidocaine + 10 ml of the solution in the small container.

The harvesting device is a 60-ml disposable Luer-lock syringe attached to a three-holed blunt cannula through the adaptor. Access to donor area is obtained by appropriately placed 1 or 2 mm incision made by # 11 blade at the most dependent area. Handling of S.C fat between thumb and index, then insertion of the harvesting device. The entry portal of the cannula is just large enough to allow passage of fatty tissue parcels of a size that then will pass through the lumen of the tip of the Luer-lock syringe. To limit the vacuum to minimal negative pressure, suction is hand applied by slowly withdrawing the plunger of the 60-ml syringe in a gradual manner, then the pulled out plunger is held in place by use of the snapper to maintain negative pressure obtained. The harvesting relies on a curretting action aided by suctioning in multiple radial pathways.⁽³⁶⁾ (fig 6)

Transfer and Purification

The harvesting cannula is disconnected from the Luer-lock and is replaced by a cap. The plunger of the syringe then is removed. The content of the 60 ml syringe is transferred manually into 10 ml luer lock syringe. The 10 ml syringe is left in vertical position. Ringer's solution and blood descend downward, and the fat as a lighter substance floats up. Ringer's solution and blood are then removed by pushing the plunger onwards after which the fat has a clean yellow white color and is ready for transplantation.⁽³⁶⁾ (fig. 7)

Figure 6: Liposuction from lower abdomen.

Figure 7: Fat parcels in vertical position in 10cc syringes.

In 3 patients among the studied group the suctioned fat was subjected to filtration in a gauze before injection, we emptied the content of the 60 ml syringe in a gauze and left to be filtered, and then we placed the clean yellowish white filtered fat parcels using a curettage spoon into the 10 ml syringe ready to be injected instead of leaving the suctioned fat to settle in inverted position in 10 ml syringe.⁽⁶³⁻⁶⁹⁾ (fig.8 a,b)

a

b

Figure 8: Filtration of fat parcels in a gauze.

Placement

The recipient area is anesthetized by local infiltration of 0.5% lidocaine with 1:200,000 of epinephrine previously prepared in the small container. The lipoinfiltrator is a 15 cms cannula with an ejection aperture close to the closed distal end. The ejection portal is just large enough to allow passage of the parcels of fatty tissue. The intact parcels are forced out of the ejection aperture by depressing the plunger on the infiltrating syringe. The size, shape, and internal finish of the cannula is designed to reduce clogging and trauma to the parcels of fatty tissue. The distal end is blunt to reduce the chance of hematomas, nerve damage, and perforation of nontargeted tissues. The cannula is connected to the 10 ml Luer lock syringe filled with refined fatty tissue.

Access to areas is obtained by appropriately placed 1-or 2-mm incisions made with a # 11 blade not in a dependent area to avoid leakage. The lipoinfiltrator is inserted through this incision to create tunnels by the advancement of the cannula through the recipient tissue. As the cannula through is withdrawn, the plunger of the syringe is depressed in a controlled manner so that a minuscule amount of the refined tissue (usually less than 1/8 of a ml) is placed evenly over the length of the tunnel. Only minimal positive pressure is ever placed on the plunger of the infiltration syringe. If any significant resistance is encountered the cannula is disconnected immediately from the syringe and any offending plug is removed.⁽³⁶⁾ (fig. 9)

Figure 9: Lipoinjection into the forehead.

Postoperative care

Compression dressings are applied around the infiltrated areas if there is any suspicion of infection in the postoperative period. Stenting of areas of particular motion such as the glabella often is preformed. Usually simple paper tape is used to stabilize these areas. For 36 to 48 hours postoperatively, cold compresses or ice packs are applied continuously on all infiltrated sites.⁽³⁶⁾

Figure 8: Application of the forehead

Results

RESULTS

RESULTS

Demographic data

Fifteen patients were included in this study.

The age of the patients ranged from 17-48 years with a mean value of 33.0 ± 10.0 years (table I).

There were 12 females (80%) and 3 males (20%) (Table I and graph 1).

The body mass index ranged from 21.6-37.1 Kg/m^2 with a mean value of $26.6 \pm 4.7 \text{ Kg/m}^2$. 4 patients (26.7%) were thin, 3 patients (20%) were normal, 5 patients (33.3%) were grade I obesity, and 3 patients (20%) were grade II obesity (table II and graph 2).

Diagnosis and Microlipoinjection

The diagnosis of the studied cases was as follows: (table III and graph 3,4):

- 1- Two patients were diagnosed as en coup de sabre (13.3%) and gave poor doctor satisfaction results .
- 2- Traumatic in three patients (20%) and gave poor doctor satisfaction results .
- 3- Natural in seven patients (46.7%) and gave very good doctor satisfaction results in four patients and excellent doctor satisfaction results in three patients .
- 4- Previous steroid therapy in three patients (20%) and gave good doctor satisfaction results in two patients and very good doctor satisfaction results in one patient.

Table I. Demographic data of studied patients

Patient no	Age (years)	Sex
1	37	Female
2	37	Female
3	39	Female
4	20	Male
5	30	Female
6	31	Female
7	25	Female
8	25	Male
9	26	Male
10	47	Female
11	17	Female
12	25	Female
13	45	Female
14	43	Female
15	48	Female
Range	17-48	12 females (80.0%)
Mean $\pm$ SD	33.0 $\pm$ 10.0	3 males (20.0%)

Graph 1. Sex distribution in studied patients

Table II. Body mass index of studied patients

Patient no	BMI (Kg/m ²)	BMI
1	32.3	Grade II obesity
2	22.3	Thin
3	30.4	Grade II obesity
4	24.4	Normal
5	21.6	Thin
6	21.8	Thin
7	22.6	Normal
8	29.1	Grade I obesity
9	29.3	Grade I obesity
10	37.1	Grade II obesity
11	22.6	Normal
12	22.0	Thin
13	29.7	Grade I obesity
14	29.0	Grade I obesity
15	25.0	Grade I obesity
Range	21.6-37.1	Thin: 4 (26.7%)
Mean ± SD	26.6 ± 4.7	Normal: 3 (20.0%)
		Grade I obesity: 5 (33.3%)
		Grade II obesity: 3 (20.0%)

Graph 2. BMI in studied patients

Table III. Indications of microlipoinjection

Patient No	Site	Symmetry	Cause
1	Forehead	Central	En coup de Sabre
2	Hollow right cheek	Unilateral	Traumatic
3	Forehead	Unilateral	Natural
4	Hollow right cheek	Unilateral	Previous steroid therapy
5	Depressive right jaw line	Unilateral	Natural
6	Upper lip augmentation	Central	Natural
7	Forehead	Central	En coup de Sabre
8	Hollow right cheek	Unilateral	Previous steroid therapy
9	Hollow left cheek	Unilateral	Previous steroid therapy
10	Depression above eye brow	Unilateral	Traumatic
11	Depression above left eyebrow	Unilateral	Traumatic
12	Prominent nasolabial folds	Bilateral	Natural
13	Deep infraorbital groove	Bilateral	Natural
14	Prominent nasolabial folds	Bilateral	Natural
15	Deep infraorbital groove	Bilateral	Natural
		Central: 3 (20%) Unilateral: 8 (53.3%) Bilateral: 4 (26.7%)	En coup de sabre: 2 (13.3%) Traumatic: 3 (20%) Natural: 7 (46.7%) Previous steroid therapy: 3 (20%)

Graph 3. Causes of microlipoinjection

Graph 4. Correlation between diagnosis and doctor satisfaction

The affected sites were all in the face, 5 patients were affected in the forehead, 5 patients were in the cheeks, one patient in upper lip, 2 patients with prominent nasolabial folds, and 2 patients with deep infraorbital grooves.

Table III summarizes the site of injection in the studied patients. The site of injection was central in 3 patients (20%), unilateral in 8 patients (53.3%) and bilateral in 4 patients (26.7%) (table III and graph 5).

The technique of liposuction was the same in all patients and from the same site (abdomen).

The technique of microlipoinjection was also the same in all patients except that the suctioned fat was subjected to filtration before injection in 3 patients instead of leaving it in the 10 ml syringe in vertical position in order to settle down in the remaining 12 patients.

The range of microlipoinjection was 2.5-20 cc with a mean value of 9.4 ± 7.1 cc (table IV) according to the indications.

Overcorrection was done in all patients ranging from 30-50% overcorrection. Five patients were subjected to nearly 30% overcorrection and 10 patients were subjected to nearly 50% overcorrection. (table IV)

Graph 5. Symmetry of site of microlipoinjection

Table IV. Microlipoinjection of studied patients

Patient no	Technique of injection	Microlipoinjection (CC)	Overcorrection
1		17.0	30%
2		20.0	50%
3		7.0	30%
4		20.0	50%
5		15.0	50%
6		3.0	30%
7	Filtration	18.0	30%
8	Filtration	15.0	50%
9	Filtration	5.0	50%
10		5.0	30%
11		4.0	50%
12		3.0	50%
13		3.0	50%
14		2.5	50%
15		3.0	50%
	Filtration: 3 (20%)	Range: 2.5-20.0	30%: 5 (33.3%)
		Mean ± SD: 9.4 ± 7.1	50%: 10 (66.7%)

Histopathology

Biopsy from the site of lipoinjection was taken from all patients at the end of the study after 6 months. Skin biopsies were examined for the presence of mature fat cells, new vessels formation, the presence of fat cysts denoting fat necrosis.

Mature fat cells were present in 10 patients (66.7%) and absent in 5 patients (33.3%) (table V and graph 6)(figure 10 a,b,c, 11,12,13 and 14).

New vessels were present in 10 patients (66.7%) and absent in 5 patients (33.3%) (table V and graph 6)(figure 12,13 and 14).

Fat cysts were mild in 8 patients (53.3%), moderate in 2 patients (13.3%) and severe in 5 patients (33.3%) (table V and graph 7) (figure 15).

In the three patients, in whom filtration technique was used for lipoinjection, the histopathology characterized by absent mature fat cells in one patient (patient number 7) and with presence of mature fat cells in 2 patients (66.6%) (patient number 8 and 9).

Follow up

In all patients, there was a temporary mild erythema and oedema at the recipient site following injection. This oedema increased during the first postoperative day and was most performed in the periorbital area. It then releaved gradually over the first postoperative week aided by the application of cold compresses. A single case of hollow right cheek complained of a palpable lump beside the right eye, it was directed to massage the area by the tips of the fingers, with gradual resolution.

Table V. Histopathology of studied patients

Patient No	Mature fat cells	New vessels	Fat cyst (denoting necrosis)
1	Absent	Absent	Severe
2	Absent	Absent	Severe
3	Present	Present	Mild
4	Present	Present	Mild
5	Present	Present	Mild
6	Present	Present	Mild
7	Absent	Absent	Severe
8	Present	Present	Moderate
9	Present	Present	Moderate
10	Absent	Absent	Severe
11	Absent	Absent	Severe
12	Present	Present	Mild
13	Present	Present	Mild
14	Present	Present	Mild
15	Present	Present	Mild
	Absent: 5 (33.3%) Present: 10 (66.7%)	Absent: 5 (33.3%) Present: 10 (66.7%)	Severe: 5 (33.3%) Mild: 8 (53.3%) Moderate: 2 (13.3%)

Graph 6. Histopathology of studied patients

Graph 7. Fat cyst in studied patients

Doctor Satisfaction

Based on the data collected during the follow up visits and documented by photography, the residual augmentation or the correction was expressed as a percentage from the initial full correction, and was recorded in the patients sheet. The correction at the end of the follow up was rated on the basis of a scale of 0-100% patients whose correction was rated 80-100% were judged to have (excellent) correction.

Those with a rating of 60-80% had very good correction, those who had 40-60% had good correction, and subjects rated less than 40% had poor correction.

The overall results of patients were as follows: poor in 5 patients (33.3%), good in 2 patients (13.3%), very good in 5 patients (33.3%) and excellent in 3 patients (20.0%) (table VI and graph 8).

The doctor satisfaction in the forehead lesion was poor in four patients (two of them were presented with en coup de sabre and the other two were presented with traumatic depressions above eyebrows) and excellent in one patient (presented with natural depression) . In the cheeks, the doctor satisfaction was poor in one patient(presented with traumatic depression) , good in two patients(presented with previous steroid atrophy induced depressions), very good in one patient (presented with previous steroid atrophy induced depression) and excellent in one patient (presented with natural depression on the right jaw line) . The doctor satisfaction was very good in the patient with upper lip lesion. The doctor satisfaction was excellent in one patient and very good in the other patient with nasolabial fold lesion (both presented with natural prominent nasolabial folds).

Table VI. Satisfaction of patients and doctors

Patient No	Patient satisfaction	Doctor satisfaction
1	Poor	Poor
2	Poor	Poor
3	Excellent	Excellent
4	Very good	very good
5	Excellent	Excellent
6	Very good	very good
7	Good	Poor
8	Good	Good
9	Good	Good
10	Poor	Poor
11	Poor	Poor
12	Excellent	Excellent
13	Very good	very good
14	Very good	very good
15	Very good	very good
	Poor: 4 (26.7%) Good: 3 (20.0%) Very good: 5 (33.3%) Excellent: 3 (20.0%)	Poor: 5 (33.3%) Good: 2 (13.3%) Very good: 5 (33.3%) Excellent: 3 (20.0%)

Graph 8. Satisfaction of patients and doctors

The doctor satisfaction was very good in the two patients presented with natural deep inferorbital groove. (graph 4,9)

In 5 patients with 30% overcorrection, doctor satisfaction was poor in 3 patients (60%) (patient number 1, 7 and 10), excellent in one patient number 3 (20%) and very good in one patient number 6 (20%). (graph 10)

In 10 patients with 50% overcorrection, doctor satisfaction was poor in 2 patients (20%) (patient number 2 and 11), good in 2 patients (20%) (patient number 8 and 9). Very good in 4 patients (40%) (patient number 4, 13, 14 and 15) and excellent in 2 patients (20%) (patient number 5 and 12). (graph 10)

In the three patients, in whom filtration technique was used for lipoinjection, the doctor satisfaction was good in 2 patients (66.6%) (patient number 8 and 9), while it was poor in one patient (33.3%)(patient number 7).

Patients Satisfaction

This denotes the degree of satisfaction expressed by patients for the augmentatory effect. Out of 15 patients, satisfaction was poor in 4 patients (26.7%); 3 of them had depressions in forehead (one presented by en coup de sabre and the other two presented by traumatic depressions above eyebrows), the fourth patient had hollow right cheek following traumatic scar. Good in 3 patients (20.0%); one patient presented by en coup de sabre (forehead) and the other two by hollow cheeks one right and the other one left.

Graph 9. Correlation between sites and doctor satisfaction

Graph 10. Correlation between overcorrection and doctor satisfaction

Very good in 5 patients (33.3%): one patient had upper lip augmentation, two patients had deep infraorbital grooves, one patient had hollow right cheek and one patient had prominent nasolabial folds and excellent in 3 patients (20.0%): one patient had prominent nasolabial folds, one patient had unilateral natural depression in the forehead on the right side and one patient had depression on the right jaw line (table VI and graph 8).

Comparison between absent mature fat cells and present mature fat cells as regards different parameters

The mean age was 32.7 ± 11.7 years in absent mature cells and 33.3 ± 9.8 years in present mature fat cells, with no significant difference between both groups ($P = 0.918$) (table VII and graph 11).

The mean BMI was 27.4 ± 6.9 Kg/m² in absent mature cells and 26.2 ± 3.6 Kg/m² in present mature fat cells, with no significant difference between both groups ($P = 0.674$) (table VII and graph 11).

The mean microlipoinjection was 12.8 ± 7.7 cc in absent mature fat cells and 7.7 ± 6.5 cc in present mature fat cells, with no significant difference between both groups ($P = 0.195$) (table VII and graph 11).

All absent mature fat cells were female, while present mature fat cells were 30% males and 70% females, with no significant difference between both groups ($P = 0.171$) (table VII and graph 12).

Table VII. Comparison between present mature fat cells and absent mature fat cells as regards different parameters

	absent mature fat cells (n = 5)	present mature fat cells (n = 10)	Statistical test
Age	32.6 ± 11.7	33.2 ± 9.8	P = 0.918
Sex			
Male	0 (0.0%)	3 (30.0%)	P = 0.171
Female	5 (100.0%)	7 (70.0%)	
BMI	27.4 ± 6.9	26.2 ± 3.6	P = 0.674
Microlipoinjection	12.8 ± 7.7	7.7 ± 6.5	P = 0.195
Patient satisfaction			
Poor	4 (80.0%)	0 (0.0%)	P = 0.007*
Good	1 (20.0%)	2 (20.0%)	
Very good	0 (0.0%)	5 (50.0%)	
Excellent	0 (0.0%)	3 (30.0%)	
Doctor satisfaction			
Poor	5 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	P = 0.0027*
Good	0 (0.0%)	2 (20.0%)	
Very good	0 (0.0%)	5 (50.0%)	
Excellent	0 (0.0%)	3 (30.0%)	

Graph 11. Comparison between present mature fat cells and absent mature fat cells as regards age, BMI and microlipoinjection

Graph 12. Comparison between present mature fat cells and absent mature fat cells as regards sex

In absent mature fat cells, patient satisfaction was poor in 80% and good in 20%. In present mature fat cells, patient satisfaction was good in 20%, very good in 50% and excellent in 30%. The patient satisfaction was significantly better in present mature fat cells patients ($P = 0.007$) (table VII and graph 13).

In absent mature fat cells, doctor satisfaction was poor in all patients. In present mature fat cells, doctor satisfaction was good in 20%, very good in 50% and excellent in 30%. The doctor satisfaction was significantly better in present mature fat cells patients ($P = 0.002$) (table VII and graph 14).

In absent mature fat cells, diagnosis were en coup de sabre in two patients, and traumatic causes of facial depressions in three patients. In present mature fat cells diagnosis was previous steroid atrophy induced depressions in three patients and natural causes of facial depressions in the remaining seven patients (graph 15) (figure 10a,b,c, 11,12,13,14 and 15).

Graph 13. Comparison between present mature fat cells and absent mature fat cells as regards patient satisfaction

Graph 14. Comparison between present mature fat cells and absent mature fat cells as regards doctor satisfaction

Graph 15. Correlation between diagnosis and histopathology

Case 1

a) Central depression in the forehead (en coup de sabre)

b) immediate postoperative.

c,d) Two weeks later.

e) Six month later.

Case 2

a) Traumatic depression of the right cheek.

b) Three month postoperative.

c) Six month later.

Case 3

a) Case with central depression in the forehead (natural).

b) Immediate postoperative.

c,d) Six month later.

Case 4

a) Steroid induced atrophy of the right cheek.

b) Immediate postoperative.

c,d) Six month later.

Case 5

a) Preoperative view: of a case of depression of the right Jaw line.

b) Immediate postoperative.

c) Six month later.

Case 7

a) Central depression in the forehead (en coup de sabre)

b) One week postoperative.

c) Six month later.

Case 10

a) Scar induced depression in the forehead.

b) Immediate postoperative.

b) Prominent nasal bridge

c,d) Six month later.

Case 12

a) Prominent nasolabial folds.

b) One week postoperative.

c) Six month later.

a,b) A case of depressed infraorbital grooves.

c,d) Six month following operation.

Figure 10 a: LPV showing scattered striated muscle bundles, showing multiple lobules of mature fat cells. (H & E stain x100)

Figure 10 b: HPV of previous case showing a mass of mature vascularized fat cells. (H & E stain x200).

Figure 10 c: Higher power view of previous case showing mature fat cells arranged in sheets separated by vascular fibrous tissue bands. (H & E stain x400)

Figure 11: LPV of striated muscle fibers showing lobules of vascularized mature fat cells. (H & E stain x100)

Figure 12: HPV of mature fat cells showing small blood vessels with intact vascular channels lined by endothelial cells. (H & E stain x400)

Figure 13: HPV of mature fat cells showing vascularization. (H & E stain x400)

Figure 14: HPV, of dense fibrous tissue bands showing two widely gapped blood vessels, no fat cells could be detected. (H & E stain x400)

Figure 15: HPV of a sheet of mature fat cells showing

- * moderate coagulative necrosis (H & E stain x400)
- * moderate necrosis: (about 50% of fields / 10 / HPFs)

Discussion

DISCUSSION

DISCUSSION

Augmentations as a mean of enhancing facial contour have been practiced for more than a century. Few disputes on the importance of restoration of atrophied subcutaneous tissue or enhancement of facial elements are still going on. However, the search for the most appropriate filler substance for use in facial remodeling has been long and hard search.⁽³⁶⁾

Autologous fatty tissue has been used successfully in recontouring since its earliest reported transfer to fill scars in 1893, however most plastic surgeons have favored non living substances for facial augmentation. Since the turn of the century, surgeons have used a bizarre palette for enhancing facial elements including gold, silver, filigree wire hard rubber, paraffin, sponge rubber, silk, gutta-percha and ivory, with the appearance of relatively inert silicone in the 1950s, attention was further directed away from autologous tissue and toward solid alloplastic implants and injectable silicone. Despite their less than ideal bioreactivity, most surgeons have continued to use alloplastic materials over autografts.⁽⁷⁰⁻⁷¹⁾

With the advent of liposuction in the 1980s, plastic surgeons became interested in re-injecting suctioned fat for soft tissue augmentation, the earliest reports were discouraging but later experiment reported variable success. All published accounts of injected fatty tissue however, demonstrate vast differences in the methods of harvesting, transfer, treatment and placement of the fat as well as varied methods of evaluating survival.^(29,30,72)

In 1986, Coleman presented specific method of autologous fatty transplantation, lipostructure, which incorporates the technique of syringe liposuction with an intricate layering of autologous fatty tissues.

Coleman has been able to document a high rate of success in the permanence of the results by focusing on the procedure as a grafting technique, and fully respecting the delicate nature of adipose tissue.⁽³⁶⁾

The aim of this study was to study the histopathological changes occurring to the transplanted fat graft after six months of lipoinjection. Correlation between these changes and other factors influencing fat survival were analyzed in order to standardize the technique and trial to elongate fat survival.

In this study, fifteen patients were included twelve females and three males. Three patients were presented with central depression needed lipoinjection, eight patients with unilateral and four with bilateral depression aiming lipoinjection.

The technique of liposuction was the same in all patients. The technique of lipoinjection was also the same in all patients except that the suctioned fat was subjected to filtration in three patients among the studied group before injection instead of leaving the suctioned fat to settle in inverted position in 10 ml syringe.

Overcorrection was done in all patients ranging from 30-50% overcorrection. Five patients were subjected to nearly 30% over correction and ten patients were subjected to 50% overcorrection.

The effect of overcorrection was also analyzed in relation to results of the study.

In this study we used lower abdomen as main site of fat obtained by liposuction in all patients included in the study.

As mentioned by Chajchir et al., in their experience with fat injection and reinjection using material obtained from different zones, they have not noticed any difference in the adipose tissue with respect to its permanence and survival. However, the choice of the donor site can be a problem because many of the patients seeking augmentation of the facial contour are very thin.^(40,73)

In general, the sites with soft and easily removable fat should be used as lower abdomen, upper inner thigh and trochanteric area.

Neichajev and Seveuk found that the fat in the femoral region is more suitable for transplantation than facial fat. Fat tissue in the lower half of the body has less connective tissue septa and thus is only sparsely vascularised. This decreases the amount of blood in suctioned fat. Extravasated blood is known to be a good media for bacterial growth.^(50,74)

In the present study, the suctioned fat was left in vertical position, so as the effect of gravity to sediment the harvested material into layers for separation of fatty tissue, the blood and Ringer's lactate solution in the bottom was discarded, the fat yellow cells on the top were reinjected at the recipient areas. However, we used the filtration method used by Kuran and Tumerdem in only three patients out of fifteen, no centrifugation of fatty tissue was done and nothing was added to fat cells after harvesting. The technique of filtration has no significant difference than sedimentations method at both histopathological results and Doctor Satisfaction results.⁽⁶²⁾

The predictability of fat grafting is enhanced if the infiltrated tissue is relatively pure fatty tissue. Thus removal of the non living components from harvested tissue is essential for accurate corrections.

Coleman mentioned that allowing gravity to sediment the harvested material into layers for separation from the fatty tissue is the simplest method of refinement. Unfortunately, the sedimentation requires considerable time. Therefore centrifugation was used to speed the process by increasing the gravitational forces applied to harvested tissue. He believes that harvested fatty tissue as intact parcels can withstand brief centrifugation obviously, if the delicate structure of fatty tissue is disrupted during harvesting or refinement, then centrifugation of the fragile fat cells can cause significant damage.^(36,75)

Abel Chajchir and Benzaquen reported in comparative experimental study of autologous adipose tissue processed by different techniques that comparing fat tissue without any treatment, fat tissue previously treated with insulin, fat tissue previously centrifuged at 500 rpm (5 min) and fat tissue previously centrifuged at 1000 rpm (5 min), they reported that the fat injected without treatment proved to be the most effective method and presented the least resorption in the biopsy specimen.

The use of insulin did not reduce the rate of resorption, on the contrary, it increased the risk of complications (postoperative hypo glucose), and centrifugation completely destroyed the adipocytes. There was no possibility of fat tissue survival. Histopathologically the differences in centrifuge speed did not produce any difference in results.⁽⁷⁵⁾

Coleman reported that every effort should be made to maintain the structure of the tissue parcels when refining the fatty tissue. Mechanical manipulations such as washing, filtering, or straining are never performed, the mechanical action of "Washing" will subject the reticular fibers and connective tissue septae to unnecessary trauma and can disrupt the fatty tissue architecture.^(36,76) Not only

mechanical maneuvers, but even exposure to ambient air will damage the harvested fat. Histologic studies have demonstrated 50% cytoplasmic lysis to fatty tissues exposed briefly to air, so exposure should be avoided whenever possible.⁽²⁷⁾

Furthermore, no chemicals, hormones, drugs or foreign substances of any type should be introduced to the transplanted tissue. Avoiding any exposure of the delicate fatty tissue to chemical or mechanical damage is essential.⁽³⁶⁾

Kuran and Tumerdem 2005 developed a simple method to prepare the fat for injection. To preserve the physiologic property of the solution, they did not add distilled water to the solution injected in the donor site; they collected the initial fat from each donor site targeted to undergo a liposuction procedure by syringe aspiration. Separation of the initial samples provided a fat graft that was bloodless and minimally traumatized. The aspirate was cleansed of local anesthetic solution by washing it with lactated Ringer's solution four or five times. After wash, the fat was not centrifuged, but left to be filtered in gauze. The idea for filtration was inspired by yogurt concentration methods used in Anatolia. They believed that this filtration method prevented the adverse effect of centrifugation.⁽⁶²⁾

In this study, we noticed differences in results depending on the site and indication of injection. As regards the sites, it was noted that the results were poor in four patients with forehead lesions which may be due to presence of disease induced atrophy like en coup de sabre; and excellent in one patient. In the cheek area results was better; poor in one patient due to previous scarring, good in two patients, very good in one patient and excellent in one patient. Upper lip augmentation showed very good result. Results were excellent in one patient and very good in another one with prominent nasolabial folds which means that results in the cheek, nasolabial folds and lip were much better than the forehead. However, the diagnosis also played an important role as disease induced atrophy like in en coup de sabre showed poor results, also traumatic causes and scars showed poor results which may be the reason of poor results in the forehead and one patient in the cheek area. But the natural causes of atrophy and the previous steroid therapy induced atrophy showed much better results.

Chajchir and Benzaquen reported that, attempts to augment tissue beyond established normal contour with fat grafting such as in the malar prominence or chin have been successful. However, loss of underlying hard or soft tissue due to trauma or disease can be returned to its normal contour by augmenting the fat tissue. After injection the change in the fat graft over time should be comparable to the change in the natural tissue at the injected zone.

Most conditions or deficiencies for which fat injection is indicated arise from ongoing conditions such as aging, muscle activity (Such as frowning or pursing of lips) and disease induced atrophy. Even lesions not caused by ongoing processes may be subject to constant dermal remodeling, as in case of immature or contracting scars. Therefore, one may expect that for a more treated lesions the fat graft will become compressed, catabolized, reorganized or otherwise altered over time, depending on the forces that are acting at the affected zone. The cumulative effect of these natural body changes will determine the extent and rate at which correction done.⁽⁴⁵⁾

Niechajev shared with Matsudo and Toledo the favorable experience in the autotransplantation of fat for the correction of skin dimples as a sequela of liposuction and the excellent experience of Wilkinson in the use of fat graft for lip

augmentation. They raised a warning regarding the use of lipoinjection for the correction of glabellar frown lines and in the periorbital area due to known four cases of unilateral blindness, all of which occurred after fat injection under the glabellar frown lines. The probable cause was fat embolism in the central retinal artery and cerebral arteries respectively^(50,77,78).

Curson Lewis saw that factors that seem to make a difference in fat cell survival include a good vascular blood supply, a firm base of bone or other stable substance, a minimal amount of scarring, minimal motion and repeated injection.

Lewis also reported that, in the face certain areas take better than others: the best is the glabellar area followed in decreasing order by the cheek, chin, nasolabial creases, lip and marionette deformity⁽⁷⁹⁾.

In our study, we performed overcorrection in all patients included. Ten patients were subjected to nearly 50% overcorrection, and five patients were subjected to nearly 30% overcorrection. In patients with 30% overcorrection doctor satisfaction was poor in 60%, excellent in 20% and very good in 20%.

However in those patients with nearly 50% overcorrection. Doctor satisfaction was poor in only 20%, good in 20%, very good in 40% and excellent in 20%, which means that more overcorrection up to 50% is better for anticipation of the degree of absorption which ranges from 30% to 60% of the grafted fatty tissue as mentioned by Chajchir and Benzaquen⁽⁴⁰⁾.

Coleman thought that, because almost all of the transplanted fatty tissue will survive, there is no need to compensate for resorption of the grafted tissue⁽³⁶⁾.

The refined material however is not pure fat, and there will be swelling at the recipient site. Therefore some over compensation is necessary. Even after refining, the material to be grafted still contains some blood, lidocaine and oil. The volume of lidocaine used for local anesthesia will change the volume of the recipient tissues. Hematomas created by the sharp needle used during local infiltration can alter dramatically the size of the area to be corrected. Immediate edema caused by forcing the blunt cannula through living tissue will obscure the amount of fatty tissue needed for a precise correction. Finally some recipient area of extreme motion such as the mouth and glabella may have a percentage forced out postoperatively by motion.

Coordinating all of these factors with the current and future desire and needs of the patient will enable the surgeon predict the volume of correction⁽³⁶⁾.

However, although Chajchir and Benzaquen reported satisfactory results in virtually all patients. They noted that they routinely transplant 50 percent more fat than they believe necessary for the desired result.⁽⁴⁰⁾

Coleman mentioned that patients often require several episodes of infiltration. Sometimes host tissues will not accept the amount of tissue needed to create the desired effect in one step. This is particularly true with deep nasolabial folds or areas of retaining ligaments the most common reason for multiple infiltrations is that the patient presented for one complaint and worked other corrections later. Also, too much fatty tissue grafted into an area can be difficult to remove, and forcing the tissue into an unyielding area can precipitate migration or necrosis⁽³⁶⁾.

Histologic studies combined with clinical outcomes have suggested that multiple stage injection of stored fat has advantages. Findings have showed that stored in a freezer is safe to use and does not harbor bacterial growth. The obvious

benefit from the use of frozen fat is that harvesting does not have to be done each time the fat is injected. Studies have shown that a high number of viable cells exist even after defrosting ^(62,80,81,82).

The results of lipofilling should be evaluated by scientific, objective means such as meticulous, extensive photography. Through careful photographic analysis the three dimensional nature of the contour changes is best documented and changes in shadows and shapes are most clearly seen.

In this study objective evaluation was attempted by use of photography for documentation of the results of this study.

Considering using the same lighting and distance in all cases using digital camera as much as possible photographs were taken preoperatively, immediately postoperatively and on monthly interval onwards. Not only photographs but also patient and doctor satisfaction were used as tools in evaluation results. Patient and doctor satisfaction were based primarily on memory and secondarily on preoperative photographs.

The overall results of doctor satisfaction were as follows, poor in five patients (33.3%), good in two patients (13.3%) very good in five patients (33.3%) and excellent in three patients (20%). The overall results of patient satisfaction were poor in four patients (26.7%), good in three patients (20%), very good in five patients (33.3%) and excellent in three patients (20%).

Illouz emphasize clinical evaluation over photography relying primarily on the patients and physicians perception in the evaluation. The goal of lipofilling is to create more attractive facial contours that are so natural that even the most meticulous observer believes the face was created initially in such a form. The physician and the patient rarely will have a precise recollection of the preoperative condition as they become accustomed to the natural new appearance of their face. This being the case, evaluation by memory or palpation is totally unreliable in successful corrections ⁽³³⁾.

Although, photography is the best mean of evaluating the results. Patient satisfaction, is the most important gauge been which to analyze the value of the procedure ⁽³⁶⁾. several methods were tried for purpose of evaluation lipofilling including MRI and computer assisted image analysis, but none gave accurate results and each method had its disadvantages ⁽⁸³⁻⁸⁶⁾.

Several histologic and pathologic studies were made to evaluate the results of lipoinjection and to study the pattern of fat survival.

In our study, biopsies from the sites of lipoinjection was taken from all patients at the end of the study after six months, skin biopsies were examined for the presence of mature fat cells, new vessels formation and fat cyst denoting necrosis. After six months mature fat cells were present in 66.7% of patients, new vessels were also evident in all patients with present mature fat cells (66.7% of patients). Necrosis of fat cells were variable, mild in eight patients, moderate in two patients and severe in five patients in whom mature fat cells and new vessels formation were really absent after six months follow up.

In the present study, patient satisfaction was poor in 80% of patients with absent mature fat cells, while it was good in 20% of patients with present mature fat cells. It was very good in 50% and excellent in 30% among same group of patients. This means that presence of mature fat cells was directly proportional with the amount of fat retained from the initial volume. This means that as the amount of fat

retained increased, levels of mature fat cells increased also patient satisfaction was significantly better.

In the present study, doctor satisfaction was poor in all patients with absent mature fat cells, while, it was good in 20% of patients with present mature fat cells in biopsy results, very good in 50% and excellent in 30% among the same group of patients. This means that doctor satisfaction was also directly proportional with presence of mature fat cells in biopsy result and hence with presence of more retained volume of fat after a period of six months. As, the amount of fat retained after six month increased, presence of mature fat cells in biopsy results was evident and doctor satisfaction level increased.

In this study, patients were divided into four groups according to diagnosis. Patients who were diagnosed as en coup de sabre, doctor satisfaction was poor in all patients. In patients who were diagnosed as traumatic cause of facial depression, doctor satisfaction was also poor, however, in other two groups with natural cause of facial depression or previous steroid therapy resulting in facial depression, doctor satisfaction was excellent in three patients (30%), very good in (50%) good in (20%) of patients.

This means that, facial depressions resulting due to previous scaring, traumatic cause or ongoing disease process, have less successful outcome than those depressions developed naturally due to aging or previous steroid therapy.

In the present study, histopathological findings were correlated with different diagnosis . In patients who were previously diagnosed as en coup de sabre there was absent mature fat cells. In patients with traumatic cause of facial depression mature fat cells were also absent after six months. However, in patients with natural cause of facial depression or previous steroid therapy resulting in facial depression mature fat cells were present after six months of lipoinjection. This means that diagnosis has an impact on outcome of results of histopathological study.

Patients with facial depression caused by previous scaring, traumatic causes, or ongoing disease process the fat graft failed to live due to extensive fibrosis present. However, in natural skin the grafted fat was able to survive in between the adjacent supporting structure forming new vessels like was the case in patient with facial depressions resulting from natural causes like aging or previous steroid therapy.

Chajchir & Benzaquen reported that biopsy specimens obtained three months after surgery showed zones of cystosteatonecrosis, lipophagic granulomas. Lymphocytes, adipocytes, giant multinucleated cells, and a great number of new vessel formation, biopsies taken from six to eight months later showed extensive fibrosis in the periphery, and finally biopsies done one year later showed large amounts of connective tissue and fibrosis reaction as the final result⁽⁴⁰⁾.

Niechajev and Seveuk calculated the diameter of fat cells from the biopsy specimens obtained from the transplanted areas. Histologic analysis showed that already after seven months the transplanted fat had an organized lobular structure containing rather small adipocytes their size of ten to seventy microns. Each lobulus contained several hundred viable fat cells and contained its own vascular net.

In the more long lived specimens pronounced fibrosis was seen between lobuli and some times slight intralobular connective tissue formation⁽⁵⁰⁾.

Aygit et al., reported that viability of adipocytes in biopsy specimens taken from transplanted fat was evident on day fifteenth. The microcysts attributable to

attributable to adipocyte degeneration were seen focally. There was foreign body reaction around the adipocytes. The densities of the capillary vessels were minimal. On day thirty the degeneration of the adipocytes was more evident. The increase in vascularity was evident, especially around the fat graft was observed. Fibrosis was also evident. Focal calcification was seen in one specimen. On day forty five and sixty the density of the capillary vessels was less and the degeneration of the adipocytes was more. Fibrosis was less than 50% and it was located in the center of fat grafts on day forty five and in both the center and the periphery of the fat grafts on day sixty. On day ninety and one hundred twenty, the density of the capillary vessels was minimal. The degenerative changes and fibrosis were more evident in the center of most of examined specimens⁽⁸⁷⁾.

In our study, parameters of age, sex and BMI had no significant difference in results of the study.

Neichajev and Seveuk mentioned that transplanted fat retained after two years which was approximately 40 or 50 % from the initial volume injected, this fat is revascularized and is susceptible to the volume changes after general weight gain by the patient. This confirm the earliest observations of Peer that free autogenous fat grafts may actually increase in size if the patient takes on increase in adiposity that effects of particular fat system from which the graft was taken⁽⁵⁰⁻⁵¹⁾.

*Summary &
Conclusions*

Summary & Conclusion

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This work attempted to study the histopathological changes occurring to fat cells after a period of six months of microlipoinjection in different sites of the face, and the effect of these changes on fat survival.

A group of fifteen patients indicated for fat transplantation was selected. Eight patients had unilateral lesions, four patients had bilateral lesions and three patients had central lesions. The whole group underwent microlipoinjection using 60 CC syringes for liposuction, and the fat injected was subjected to filtration using a gauze in three patients and left to settle in vertical position in the remaining twelve patients. The suctioned fat was reinjected in all patients using 10 CC syringes connected to blunt cannula. Both liposuction and lipoinjection were done under local anesthesia. The lower abdomen area was used as the donor site in all patients.

The subjects were photographed before and after the procedure and during the follow up period, which lasted for six months, and then all the patients were subjected for biopsy taking from the site of lipoinjection for histopathological study.

The patients were evaluated monthly during this period, and their results were recorded based on the patients recorded data and their photographs, their end correction was divided into four categories; excellent, very good, good and poor, regarding doctor and patient satisfaction. Also, the changes occurring in fat cells were recorded after biopsy taking at the end of period of follow up.

Although this work was not designed to study these variables, an attempt was made to correlate the end correction with patients' age, body constitution, the site and the indication for injection.

By applying statistical tests on the results obtained, no association was found between these variables and the end correction due to the small size of the sample. It was noticed, however, that the correction in all patients was better achieved in immobile areas, such as the infraorbital depressions, cheeks, nasolabial folds.

Also, it was noticed that natural causes of facial depressions, previous steroid atrophy induced depressions have better results than traumatic causes and previous scarring induced depressions. It was also noticed direct statistical correlation between presence of mature fat cells in biopsy taken and the end correction results.

The side effects encountered were minimal and were mostly reversible. Most of the patients were satisfied by the results obtained.

From this study we can conclude that:

- 1- Injection of fat obtained by liposuction and used as an autologous graft has become a more frequent procedure in plastic surgery for improvements in the face and body contour to eliminate deep defects in the skin surface for cosmetic and reconstructive purposes.
- 2- The most frequent regions treated were cheeks, nasolabial folds, forehead and infra orbital areas.
- 3- Strict sterile technique always must be observed.
- 4- The predictability of fat grafting is enhanced if the infiltrated tissue is relatively pure fatty tissue. Thus removal of the non living components from harvested tissue is essential for accurate corrections.
- 5- Results in the cheek, nasolabial folds and lip were much better than the forehead. However, the diagnosis also played an important role as disease

induced atrophy like in en coup de sabre showed poor results also traumatic causes and scars showed poor results which may be the reason of poor results in the forehead and one patient in the cheek area. But the natural causes of atrophy and the previous steroid therapy induced atrophy showed much better results.

- 6- More overcorrection up to 50% is better for anticipation of the degree of absorption which ranges from 30% to 60% of the grafted fatty tissue.
- 7- In patients with facial depression caused by previous scaring, traumatic causes, or ongoing disease process the fat graft failed to live due to extensive fibrosis present. However, in natural skin the grafted fat was able to survive in between the adjacent supporting structure forming new vessels like was the case in patient with facial depressions resulting from natural causes like aging or previous steroid therapy.

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